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Biodiesel Production

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Bachelor of science in Pharmaceutical and Chemical Engineering

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I certify that the intellectual content of this thesis is the product of my own work and that all the assistance received in preparing this thesis and sources have been acknowledged.

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Abstract

With the increasing demand for fossil fuel diesel that has occurred recently, that is met with limited resources. The world has turned to look for more sustainable alternatives, and biodiesel is one of them.

Biofuel or biodiesel are ester-based fuels manufactured from animal fats or vegetable oils such as sunflower oil. Biodiesel is considered to be a renewable and efficient source for powering diesel engines. There are several methods to produce biodiesel and one of them is a transesterification reaction of the feedstock with alcohol with the aid of an alkaline catalyst.

When this reaction is performed accurately it can lead to a high conversion percentage which can go up to 98%.

This study lays out a simple overview of biodiesel production. The concept of using vegetable oils to power engines began in the late 1800s with Rudolf diesel, and scientists to this day are putting efforts to

Upgrade its properties. This work will demonstrate how sunflower oil can be modified into biodiesel using alcohol and a catalyst.

Catalysts can be divided into 3 types which are Homogenous, heterogeneous, and enzymatic. Homogeneous catalysts are the most commonly used in the transesterification reaction for their ability to speed up the reaction at normal levels of temperature and pressure, attain high yield values, and their availability for a lower cost. A homogeneous catalyst can be acidic or basic. In this work, a basic homogenous catalyst is used which is NaOH.

The ethanol (alcohol used)/ oil ratio and weight of the used catalyst are variables that affect the properties of the produced biodiesel in addition to the yield percentage. In this experiment, biodiesel is tested for its quality by measuring the density, viscosity, and refractive index. From experimental results the ethanol: oil ratio affects the yield value significantly. It was also noticed that with increasing the catalyst weight the yield value increases. Each sample takes approximately 2 hours to prepare and manufacture.

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Abbreviations and Symbols

NaOH: Sodium Hydroxide

B20: Biodiesel blend with diesel by 20%

Mph: miles per hour

CO: Carbon oxide

PAHs: Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

FAAEs: Fatty acid alkyl esters

FAs: Fatty acids

SiO₂: Silicon dioxide

Al₂O₃: Aluminum oxide

GC: Gas chromatography

ASTM: American Society for testing and materials

Wt. %: weight percentage

FFAs: Free fatty acids

GCV: Gross calorific value

RPM: round per minute

CP: Centipoise

KOH: Potassium hydroxide

ρ : Density (kg/m³)

M: Mass of the liquid (kg)

V: Volume of the liquid (m³)

η : Viscosity (cp)

K: Constant for the ratio between oil and ethanol

T: Time

TAGs: Triacylglycerol's

Mol: mole, unit to measure the amount of a substance

Ml: Milliliter

G: Grams

K: Kilogram

B100: Pure biodiesel

CHAPTER I: Introduction

General

In modern-day society, energy is an essential element for most if not all activities. Energy highlights its importance for its use in maintaining a sustainable development for mankind. There is a variety of energy sources, energy sources are mainly divided into two main classifications: Non-Renewable energy that cannot be used multiple times, unlike the other classification which is Renewable energy.

Non-renewable energy is generally considered a superior option to renewable energy, which falls back to the fact that non-renewable energy, comes from a reliable source and is not subjected to external conditions. Nonetheless, this type of energy resource is limited, it would take thousands of years to regenerate the quantities that are being consumed nowadays, and non-renewable energy is derived from fossil fuels in their different forms such as Petroleum, Natural Gas, and Coal. Studies confirm that in less than 50 years the world's reservoir will end, which will leave the world in complete darkness unless other alternatives were used.

The world now acknowledges the importance of renewable energy, not only for the above-mentioned reasons. Non-renewable energy has significantly increased the quantities of greenhouse gases above the limit, which in return increased the amount of heat that is trapped inside the atmosphere resulting in the Global Warming phenomena that alter the climate system of the planet.

Scientists around the world are developing alternatives to replace the need for fossil fuels to sustain life on this planet; one of these alternatives is Biodiesel. This will be the topic of this thesis. Biodiesel is a substitute fuel for engines that operate on diesel, which is the product of a chemical reaction of an alcohol with vegetable oil or the extract of animal fat; in addition to that a catalyst is needed to complete the reaction to produce Methyl Ester compounds, these compounds are known to be Biodiesel.

Common vegetable oils are known to be the feedstock to produce biodiesel; this includes sunflower, coconut, soybean, and canola. Other than vegetable oil biodiesel can be produced from (tallow) which is animal fat and even from used frying oils that are considered waste. The quality of the feedstock and its origin can lead to a change in the production procedure. As for the used alcohol Methanol is mainly used for its low price, but other alcohols can be used to produce biodiesel fuel with additional enhanced properties such as *Isopropanol* or ethanol.

Many countries around the world have integrated biodiesel in their transportation systems but not completely, as they would mix 20% of the produced biodiesel with 80% Petroleum diesel, those blends are indicated by acronyms such as B20. The United States of America is considered a leading country with a production rate of 1347.3 *petajoules* in 2020 only; other examples are Brazil, Indonesia, and Germany. Using biodiesel has proved statistically in those countries to decrease the financial cost of importing Petrol in addition to decreasing the emissions from different transportation modes. On the other hand, Jordan has a 0 production rate for biodiesel even though Jordan can be considered suitable to produce biodiesel and achieve financial profit, this was the interior motive behind choosing this thesis topic, to state the facts and simplify the process of producing biodiesel; hence Jordan can thrive and flourish form its resources.

Figure 1: feedstock percentages for biodiesel worldwide

Figure 2: Biofuel production by region

Brief History on Biodiesel

Since the dawn of human beings, prior to uncovering fossil fuels in the world. Early men used wood and other plants for warmth and food preparation, in other words, organic materials supplied them with the energy that was needed. In 1826 Samuel Morey the American inventor was inspired to build a combustion engine with ethanol and turpentine (oil that is harvested from living trees) as the operating fuel; the American inventor has succeeded in operating a boat with a speed of 7-8 mph. Years later many inventors around the world succeeded with similar trials but many obstacles were raised with the Civil war in America which caused the taxation of alcohol which is an essential element in biodiesel preparation. With the emergence of Gasoline in the 1910s, scientists including Alexander Graham Bell highlighted the importance of alcohol in the fuel industry. In 1918 an article was published in the Scientific American that studied the effectiveness of a fuel blend after experimenting which was (50% alcohol, 25% benzol, and 25% Gasoline) that could solve the problem of the diminishing the oil reserves. Continuous efforts were made over the last century to reduce the number of fossil fuels used.

Research in 2015 concluded that a percentage of fossil fuels should remain underground to sustain life on planet earth and suggested that the peak of extraction should be in this decade and not later on.

Figure 3: Design of Diesel's first engine

Fossil Fuels and Biodiesel on Health

A high percentage of air pollutants are generated by the combustion of different forms of fossil fuels such as Gasoline, Natural Gas, Diesel Fuel, Coal, and oil that are used in different aspects to provide energy in various forms such as transportation and heating. Although it's an efficient energy source, it's responsible for the existence of materials that are toxic and harmful to human beings such as sulfur dioxide, black carbon, nitrogen oxide, mercury, and other volatile chemicals that are major health issues to children.

Those toxic and harmful pollutants mostly affect infants and young children due to their biological and psychological vulnerability in addition to the fact that children breathe more air/k more than adults this problem is considered to be the most significant threat to their health. Fossil fuel combustion by-products can cause Dementia and Respiratory illness.

Meanwhile, the composition of biodiesel emissions contained less particulate matter, CO, and PAHs. In addition to that Compounds that contain sulfur are undetectable. Nevertheless, like any other combustion process, Biodiesel combustion can affect health but at the same time, it produces soluble organic compounds. There is insufficient information that concerns the effect of biodiesel on Human Health; further studies should be made to be aware of all the effects.

Efficiency of Biodiesel

While non-edible and edible oils and different types of blends, it was noticed that it reduces the engine efficiency due to the reduced atomization of the fuel and the quality of injection spray. Biodiesel has a higher viscosity than normal diesel which leads to the plugging of the fuel filter and a delayed injection of the fuel. Results differ with the change of the feedstock oil, engine type, and the operating conditions, it was reported that oils that contain a high percentage of glycerides mayhap cause a formation of deposits in the nozzles of the injector, valves, and pistons. Repetitive plugging of fuel filters increases the percentage of energy losses through the system, various processes were developed to lower the viscosity and improve quality such as; transesterification, micro-emulsification, and pyrolysis.

Transesterification is the most implemented method, oil molecules in general are made of triglycerides, which are made of fatty acids (FAs) and glycerol. FAs are simply Carboxylic acids in addition to a long aliphatic chain, which can be saturated or unsaturated. In the process of transesterification, alcohol will react with the triglycerides with the aid of a catalyst, enzyme, or an acid to produce (FAAEs) fatty acid alkyl esters.

Another method to reduce the viscosity of the oil is to preheat the oil until it reaches a similar viscosity to diesel fuel.

Engines performance and studies of emissions reveal that after the development of biodiesel it can be a better alternative than diesel. Biodiesel can be utilized on a small scale such as on farms and an industrial scale for operating machines. Biodiesel should be looked at in a serious matter for energy sustainability.

Objective of Study

The main objective of the research is to assess the process of producing biodiesel.

The specific objectives are:

- To evaluate the difference of the feedstock, Catalysts and alcohol used in the process and their effect on the efficiency.
- To evaluate the testing methods and the parameters that should be followed.
- To evaluate improvements that should be made for development.

Limitations of Study

The limitations of study are as follows:

- The time available is not sufficient for in depth study.
- There are no biodiesel production factories locally to further assess this study.
- Limited resources.

Organization of the Report

The report has been divided in five chapters.

Chapter I Introduction: This chapter mainly projects the difference between biodiesel and diesel, historical background on the subject, objectives and limitations of study.

Chapter II Literature Review: This chapter is dedicated to illustrate the relevant literatures and the recent works related to the study.

Chapter III Materials and Methodology: The materials used and methodologies adopted for the study is described in this chapter. The study parameters and test methods are given briefly in this chapter.

Chapter IV Results and Discussion: The analysis of test results, tables and figures are presented in this chapter.

Chapter V Conclusion and Recommendations: The conclusion of study and recommendations are given in this chapter.

The detail result sheets, photographs etc. are given in the appendix.

CHAPTER II: Literature Review

Introduction

Biodiesel is an alternative diesel fuel produced from renewable biological sources such as vegetable oils and animal fats. It is biodegradable and non-toxic, has low emission profiles and so is environmentally beneficial (Krawczyk, 1996).

One hundred years ago was the beginning of the concept of biodiesel. Vegetable oils and animal fat were used instead of diesel fuel in emergencies. Recently the conception of biodiesel has reemerged with the increase in crude oil prices, environmental concerns, and limitation of fossil fuel resources.

Natural oils from vegetables and animal fats are pressed or extracted to obtain fats and oil. Impurities such as; water, free fatty acids, sterols, phospholipids, and others exist after the extraction process, even with purifying the extracted oils a small percentage of water and fatty acids will remain in the oils which will result in a significant effect on the transesterification process.

Natural glycerides contain a high amount of unsaturated fatty acids, which makes them in a state of liquidity at room temperature. However, fats contain a high amount of saturated fatty acid, in other words at room temperature fats will be in a solid-state. This makes natural glycerides a more suitable option as a feedstock for biodiesel.

Biodiesel features

Generally biodiesel properties are dependent on the used feedstock (tallow, vegetable oils), biodiesel is characterized with important properties such as:

- Can be used in its pure form or as a blend with regular diesel.
- Can be used unmodified in diesel engines
- Can be stored in petro diesel containers
- Improve the combustion process. Due to the fact that biodiesel contain more oxygen than diesel.
- Produce fewer emissions by 50%.
- Works as a lubricant for moving engines
- Biodegradable
- Doesn't contain sulfur. Hence, no sulfur emissions will be emitted in the combustion process.

- Less flammable compared to diesel.
- Transport and storage of biodiesel are less dangerous compared to diesel due to its high flash point which is 170C.
- Doesn't irritate the skin
- More pleasant aroma
- Biodiesel contributes to rural and agriculture development.

Table 1: Comparison between fossil fuel diesel, pure biodiesel and B20 blend. In regards of carbon oxide (g/kg), hydrocarbons (g/kg), nitrogen oxides (g/kg) and particles (g/kg).

Fuel	CO (g/kg)	Total HC (g/kg)	NOx (g/kg)	Particles (g/kg)
Diesel	0.634	0.146	0.986	0.083
B20	0.574	0.128	0.991	0.078
B100	0.497	0.058	1.025	0.072

Advantages and Disadvantages of Biodiesel

Vegetable oils' advantages as diesel fuel:

- It has a liquid nature and can be ported easily.
- High heat content (80% more than the normal diesel fuel), helps to regulate the rate at which air changes temperature.
- Availability and renewability
- Environmentally friendly

Vegetable oils are disadvantages to diesel fuel:

- High viscosity value compared to diesel, due to the presence of stronger interparticle forces (dipole-dipole).
- Low volatility; is due to the increase of the molecular mass cause the larger the molecules the higher the chance to participate in more intermolecular bonding. This makes it less flammable, thus a slower combustion process.

- Unsaturated hydrocarbon chains are highly reactive and undergo multiple reactions to their multiple bonds.

A long-term study concerning the effect of the usage of biodiesel on engines was made, like any other prototype of a product issues will be involved, following are some examples

In the short term there were three main problems, which are:

- In cold seasons, the viscosity rises, and the cetane level and the flash point were significantly low. This problem can be solved by preheating the fuel before usage in addition to alternating the fuel chemically with an ester.
- Plugging and gumming of different parts of the fueling system; are caused mainly by the natural gums that exist in vegetable oils. This problem can be simply solved by refining the oil and then filtering it to 4 microns.
- Engine knocking is caused by the extremely low level of cetane and the improper injection speed. This is solved by adjusting the injection speed to be suitable for this specific type of fuel and as mentioned earlier altering the fuel chemically to an ester.

In the long term the problems with using biodiesel were more concerning, which are:

- Coking of the injectors on the piston and the head of the engine
- Carbon deposits on the piston and the head of the engine
- Excessive engine wear
- The failure of the engine lubricating oil due to polymerization; a polymerization is a group of small molecules, called monomers or building blocks, are chemically combined to create larger molecules or a macromolecule.

All these problems go back to the same reason which is the high viscosity of oil, the fuel doesn't complete the combustion process fully. These problems can be solved by preheating the fuel before usage, switching to diesel fuel when the engine is being operated at part load and last altering the fuel chemically to an ester. Additives can be used to enhance fuel properties.

Difference between petroleum diesel and biodiesel

Biodiesel is composed from Fatty acid alkyl esters whereas regular diesel fuel comprises pure hydrocarbons. Biodiesel molecules contain unsaturated ‘olefin’ components whereas petroleum diesel consists of approximately 95% saturated hydrocarbons and 5% aromatic compounds.

Fuel	Renewable	Structure	Origin	Viscosity	Freezing point	Energy density (MJ/kg)
Biodiesel	Yes	<p style="text-align: center;">ester functional group</p>	Plant matter	Relatively high	Relatively high	38
Petrodiesel	No		Fossil fuels	Relatively low	Relatively low	43

Figure 4: Comparison between biodiesel and petrodiesel

Methods for enhancing biodiesel

Thermal Cracking (pyrolysis)

The simple definition of Pyrolysis is the conversion of one substance into another using heat only or heat in addition to a catalyst in the absence of air which will yield small molecules. When this reaction occurs there are a variety of paths that can be taken and a variety of products that can be produced. The feedstock for this reaction is a wide range of varieties such as animal fat, vegetable oils, natural or synthesized fatty acids, and methyl esters. One hundred years ago the synthesis of fat was studied in areas of the world where petroleum deposits were absent. And as mentioned earlier the synthesis of vegetable oils began in the early 1910s, mainly due to the losses around the world during the First World War, many oils were tested such as soybean. After the thermal decomposition of Soybean oil, it was distilled using air, and nitrogen spurge with an ASTM apparatus, and the identified hydrocarbons after the distillation were approximately 80-88%. The main components were alkenes and alkanes which accounted for 60% of the wt%, and carboxylic acids with 9.6-16.1% of wt. %.

Figure 5: The Mechanism of thermal Decomposition of triglycerides (Schwab et al., 1988).

Later on, the thermal cracking was studied in expansion, oils were heated to 450°C with the presence of a catalyst which was SiO₂/Al₂O₃, this process has produced gases, solids, and liquids with a lower molecular weight, and the condensed organic phase was separated to produce biodiesel. The chemical composition using GC apparatus was identified and it was similar to the chemical composition of fossil fuels. The following table demonstrates the properties of soybean oil before and after the pyrolysis procedure in comparison with diesel fuel. As described this process is considered to be simple and effective, with no water and air pollution.

Table 2: Properties of thermally cracked Soybean oil

	Soybean oil		Cracked soybean oil		Diesel fuel	
	a	b	a	b	a	b
Cetane number	38.0	37.9	43.0	43.0	51.0	40.0
Higher heating value, MJ/kg	39.3	39.6	40.6	40.3	45.6	45.5
Pour point C	-12.2	-12.2	4.4	7.2	-6.7 max	-6.7 max
Viscosity, cSt at 37.8°C	32.6	32.6	7.74	10.2	2.82	1.9-4.1

^a Data from Niehaus et al. (1986).

^b Data from Schwab et al. (1988).

Rapeseed oil went through the pyrolysis process with a mixture of methyl esters in a tubular reactor at a temperature range between 500 and 850°C with the presence of nitrogen. It was observed with the increase in temperature the conversion of methyl

colzate also increased. At high temperatures the yield percentage of light hydrocarbons was high.

Results of the pyrolysis process are considered to be great results but this method is not widely used to the high prices of the equipment in addition to that removing the oxygen during thermal processing removes the environmental benefits.

Micro-emulsification

A method was created to solve the issue regarding the high viscosity of vegetable oils. The micro-emulsion was reported first in the 1980-the 1990s using active agents such as Octanol, Butanol, and FFAs. This method is simply mixing the non-polar oil phase with a polar solvent such as ethanol or water in the presence of surfactants and surfactants.

Although water is the most commonly used solvent, researchers emphasize that using ethanol as the solvent is a better option due to the fact that ethanol offers a higher calorific value GCV than water. This system provides the system with a fuel that has a thermodynamically stable colloidal dispersion with a droplet size of 1-150nm. The polar solvent disperses in a continuous oil phase to form a system w/o micro-emulsion type, dispersion occurs due to the reduction of the interfacial tension between the two phases. Studies suggest that fuel that has gone through the micro-emulsion process has a lower combustion temperature, which in turn reduces the harmful emissions that are usually produced like CO, NO_x, and PM.

The selection process of the surfactant or the co-surfactant is considered to be a challenge, it's important to use a non-ionic/ bio-based surfactant that contains neither nitrogen nor sulfur to support one of the reasons for the production of biodiesel which is environmental sustainability.

The quality of the produced product exhibited great results, but this method is considered to be none effective method due to its high energy consumption and highly-priced.

Figure 6: Micro emulsion process to produce low viscosity biodiesel

Transesterification (alcoholysis)

Transesterification is a reaction of oil or fat with an alcohol to form esters and glycerol, a catalyst that can be used to boost the reaction rate and yield. Many alcohols can be used in this reaction such as propanol, ethanol, methanol, butanol, etc., but methanol is most frequently to be used due to its low price in addition to its chemical and physical advantages (short-chain and polar alcohol). It has a quick reaction speed with triglycerides and the NaOH can be easily dissolved in it. The catalyst can be acids, alkalis, or enzymes. Acids such as Sulfonic Acid, Sulfuric acid, and hydrochloric acid. Alkalis such as NaOH and KOH. If the chosen catalyst is Alkalis the reaction rate is faster than when using acid as the catalyst. This reaction is reversible, excess alcohol should be added to shift the equilibrium to the products.

When alkalis are used as the catalyst in the transesterification process, alcohol and glycerol must be anhydrous because water can partially change the reaction into saponification which means soap will be produced. The formation of soap will lower the yield percentage of esters and makes the washing of esters and glycerol and water difficult. Low FFAs (Free Fatty Acids) content is required in triglycerides for this reaction.

When the physical properties of the primary alcohol product in this process it was noticed that the boiling point of methyl esters, fatty acids, and the present glycerides increases with the increase of the carbon chain. The melting points for the glycerides present increased because of the polarity of the hydrogen bonding and molecules.

Obtaining pure esters is difficult due to the impurities that are present in the esters such as di-, and tri- glycerides. The mono-glycerides caused crystals formation in the mixture of the ester. The by-product which is glycerol is recovered because of its value in the chemical industry.

Mechanism and kinetics

Transesterification process consists of consecutive and reversible reactions.

Triglycerides \rightarrow di-glycerides \rightarrow mono-glycerides \rightarrow glycerol

A mole of ester will be freed at each step, this reaction is reversible but as mentioned earlier excess alcohol should be added to shift the equilibrium towards the products. The mechanism of alkali catalyzed reaction consists of three steps. Firstly, the anion of the alcohol will attack the carbonyl carbon atom that is in the triglycerides to form a tetrahedral intermediate. Secondly, the alcohol will react with the tetrahedral intermediate to regenerate the alcohol anion. Lastly, a rearrangement will occur to the tetrahedral intermediate which will result in the formation of di-glycerides and fatty acids. A small amount of water will be generated which might cause the formation of soap.

Where R-OH diglyceride, R₁ long chain alkyl group, and R' short alkyl group

Figure 7: Mechanism of the transesterification reaction with alcohol and an alkali catalyst.

As mentioned earlier the catalysts for the transesterification reaction can be alkali, acid, or an enzyme. Although the alkali catalyst can speed up the reaction, if the glyceride used has a high fatty acid content and water; acid as a catalyst would be more suitable for the reaction.

Transesterification reaction can occur at different temperatures, depending on the used oil. For example, when using castor oil the reaction started at a temperature of 20-35°C with a molar ratio of 6:1-12:1. When soybean oil has experimented it resulted in values that suggest the higher the temperature the higher the yield percentage will be. Noting that the accepted molar ratio is 6:1.

Figure 8: Process flow diagram for biodiesel production using heterogeneous base catalyst.

Figure 9: Process Flowchart

Enzymatic transesterification for biodiesel production

In the transesterification reaction, a catalyst is needed to enhance the process. Catalysts are divided into 3 types which are Homogenous, heterogeneous, and enzymatic.

Enzymatic catalysts are Lipases. Lipases can be found in plants, animals, and microorganisms. Lipases play a key role in the metabolism process of oils and fats as they take a part in the transfer, deposition, and metabolism of lipids. They can catalyze a variety of reactions.

Lipase offers the following benefits:

- Lower energy requirement
- Higher product yield
- No wastewater generation
- The pure quality of biodiesel and glycerol
- Easy recovery of products

Nevertheless, enzymatic catalysts are pricy and have a longer reaction time.

Economic Analysis

To have a full economic analysis the following factors should be considered:

- Raw materials costs
- Production and storage costs
- Marketing and distribution costs

Raw material Cost

Feedstock:

Table 3: Feedstock for biodiesel production prices \$/L.

Feedstock type	Cost \$/L
Sunflower Oil	0.56\$/L
Soybean Oil	0.808\$/L
Coconut Oil	5.5\$/L
Tallow	0.80\$/L

Olive Oil	10\$/L
Palm Oil	0.64\$/L
Rapeseed Oil	3.25

Alcohol:

Table 4: Alcohol used in biodiesel production prices \$/L.

Alcohol Type	Price \$/L
Methanol	0.25\$/L
Ethanol	1.52\$/L

Catalyst:

Table 5: Catalysts used in biodiesel production prices \$/L

Catalyst	Price \$/L
KOH	0.50\$/L
NaOH	0.17\$/L

Distilled water: 0.18\$/L

Phosphoric Acid: 0.73\$/L

Production Costs:

Table 6: Inputs in the biodiesel production process and the quantities of each per unit volume of biodiesel (L) with the total cost(\$/L)

Inputs	Unit	Quantity per unit volume of biodiesel (L)	Total cost \$/L
Human Labor	(h)	0.036	0.33
Electricity	(kWh)	0.013	0.07

Machinery	(h)	0.009	0.03
Service and maintenance	Year	0.122	0.0001

Total cost of 1 liter of Biodiesel is 1.6\$/L.

Products selling costs:

Table 7: Outputs of the biodiesel production process and the quantities of each per unit volume of biodiesel (L) with the total selling cost (\$/L).

Outputs	Unit	Quantity per unit volume of biodiesel (L)	Total cost \$/L
Biodiesel	(L)	1.000	2.45
Glycerol	(L)	0.105	0.03
Alcohol	(L)	0.110	0.03
Water	(L)	0.001	0.0002
Soap	(L)	0.019	0.021

Total selling cost of the products is 2.5132\$/L

Benefit = Income - Costs

$$Benefit = 2.5132 - 1.6 = 0.9132\$/L$$

CHAPTER III: Materials and Methodology

Materials

As known, biodiesel can be produced from a variety of raw materials such as; animal fats, soybean oil, canola oil..etc. After conducting research on different types of raw materials regarding their availability, bulk cost, and convenience. Sunflower oil was found to be the optimum raw material for this research.

The production of biodiesel from sunflower oil, ethanol, and a catalyst (NaOH) was added to the reaction. The reaction was performed as a laboratory experiment to analyze and study the effect of changing the ratio of the three variables (oil, alcohol, catalyst) on the quality and the yield percentage of the produced biodiesel.

List of the chemicals, glassware and equipment used:

Chemicals

- Ethanol (C₂H₅OH)
- Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH)
- Phosphoric Acid (H₃PO₄)

Glassware and Equipment

- Electronic balance
- Hot plate magnetic stirrer
- Thermometer
- Magnet
- Beaker
- Graduated Cylinder
- Erlenmeyer flask
- Test tube
- Viscometer
- Refractometer

Experimental procedure

Ethanol and Sodium hydroxide are mixed in a flask in low-level moisture conditions*, then placed in a water bath at a temperature of 50°C in addition to stirring the mixture at a constant speed until the sodium hydroxide has completely dissolved in the ethanol. Simultaneously 200 ml of sunflower oil is heated at 60°C and the temperature is measured using a thermometer. Afterward, the ethanol-Sodium hydroxide mixture is added to the heated sunflower oil in a flask and then placed in a water bath at a temperature of 50°C with stirring at 500 rpm, visible change is noticed in 60 minutes.

The product solution is then poured into a separatory funnel; the mixture should be mixed with constant ventilation to expel excess gases. After some time, two layers will be distinguishable with a top layer of biodiesel and a bottom layer of the by-product which is Glycerol. The bottom layer is removed and measured to calculate the percentage yield of the reaction.

The produced biodiesel is mixed with Phosphoric acid to eliminate unwanted residues. This step should be repeated multiple times to ensure the purity of the produced product. The amount of the produced biodiesel is then measured to complete the calculations.

The properties of the product are then analyzed and compared to study the effect of different ratios of the main components on its quality.

*the presence of water or moisture can lead to the formation of soap by saponification

Table 8: represents the volume of ethanol and weight of the catalyst for each sample.

Sample #	Ethanol Volume (ml)	Sunflower oil Volume (ml)	Total Volume (ml)	Catalyst weight (g)
1	60	200	260	0.8
2	90	200	290	0.8
3	120	200	320	0.8
4	60	200	260	1.0
5	90	200	290	1.0
6	120	200	320	1.0
7	60	200	260	1.2
8	90	200	290	1.2
9	120	200	320	1.2
10	60	200	260	1.5
11	90	200	290	1.5
12	120	200	320	1.5

Methods of data analysis

In the production of biodiesel, several tests should be made at each step of the procedure to ensure a production of high quality biodiesel to help in detecting any problems in the production.

Stage 1

Prior to the production, the used oil should be tested for its water content. If the water content of the used oil is relatively high, the water will mix with the catalyst that is used (sodium hydroxide) which will result in the formation of soap by saponification. The formed soap will extract the catalyst, thus the catalyst will not be able to react with the oil. This will result in unsuccessful conversion of fuel. In addition this may lead to emulsion throughout the washing process.

Water in oil contamination is prone to occur, but because the water is dispersed molecule by molecule, it won't be visible to see with the naked eye. For this reason, oil can contain a significant amount of dissolved water with no visible indication of its presence.

There are several simple tests that can be constructed to ensure a low level of water content.

- Test 1 (Hot Pan Test)

After measuring the appropriate amount of oil, oil is poured into a heated pan. If the oil forms bubbles, produces steam or crackles, it means that the oil used contained water. This method is 0.05% accurate.

- Test 2 (Quantitative water test)

After measuring the appropriate amount of oil, oil is heated up to 120°C. Temperature should be measured with a thermometer. After the oil has reached the targeted temperature, oil should cool down for at least 10 minutes. The sample is then reweighed to measure the lost water content. The accuracy of this method depends on the used measuring devices.

Since all samples of oil were taken from the same container, only one sample was tested.

In addition to water content, the used oil should be tested for its acidity. In the production of biodiesel a strong base is added as a catalyst such as sodium hydroxide. If the acidity

of the used oil is high it should be compensated by adding additional catalyst to ensure the occurrence of the reaction to produce biodiesel.

This test can be carried out using a pH meter.

Furthermore, the used alcohol should be also tested for its purity if not purchased recently. When alcohol is sat for long periods of time it can absorb the moisture from air. This test can be carried out using a hydrometer. In this experiment this step was not necessary because it was purchased a day prior to the experiment.

Stage 2

Prior to washing the produced biodiesel with phosphoric acid, the product should be tested to measure and identify if it has converted successfully. Poorly reacted biodiesel can cause the formation of emulsion in the washing process. If the biodiesel has not fully converted the process should be repeated.

A simple and accurate test is made with the following steps;

- Measure 27ml of alcohol (ethanol) and 3ml of the produced biodiesel.
- The alcohol and the produced biodiesel are then mixed for approximately 30-60 sec
- Allow the mixture to sit for 5 minutes

The alcohol should absorb the biodiesel completely with no visible fall outs. The presence of fall outs indicates a failed sample of biodiesel.

Stage 3

After washing the produced biodiesel, it should be tested for its soap content. After proper washing the soap levels should be reduced greatly and minimized if the soap content is considered relatively high after washing, the washing step can be repeated multiple times.

Test 1

- Mix 10 ml of biodiesel with 100ml of isopropyl alcohol.
- Add 17 drops of Bromophenol blue.

- Slowly add measured amounts of hydrochloric acid until the mixture turns yellow in color.

The used amount of hydrochloric acid is recorded for the calculations of soap content.

One of the sample were tested it required approx. 0.12 ml of hydrochloric acid to turn yellow. This value falls within the limit which is approx. 0.1348ml.

Density

Density of the produced biodiesel is an important parameter that impacts the quality of the fuel. As mentioned earlier the density of the fuel that circulates in the injection systems and pumps should not exceed a certain limit to deliver the proper amount of fuel to the combustion without any delays. Biodiesels from different oil sources should obtain a density range between 808.0-893.23 kg / m³ at a temperature between 0-100 C. The density of a proper manufactured biodiesel is similar to fossil fuel diesel.

Density can be determined by the following equation:

$$\rho = \frac{M}{V}$$

Where:

- ρ : Density (kg/m³)
- M: Mass of the liquid (kg)
- V: Volume of the liquid (m³)

Viscosity

Viscosity is another important parameter that should be measured and controlled. A high viscous fuel will lead to improper atomization which leads to incomplete combustion.

Viscosity can be measured using a falling sphere viscometer, with the aid of the following relation:

$$\eta = k. t. (\rho_{\text{sphere}} - \rho_{\text{biodiesel}})$$

Where:

- η : Viscosity (cP)
- k: Constant
- t: Time
- ρ : Density (g/ml)

The constant in the equation is unknown; hence another medium with known viscosity and density can be used to identify the constant value.

Figure 10: Falling sphere Viscometer to measure the viscosity.

Viscosity can also be measured directly using an advanced viscometer.

Figure 11: Digital Viscometer to measure the viscosity

Refractive index

Refractive index is a measurement used for the identification of a substance. The value is then compared to known literature values. Refractive index value is also used to test the purity of the substance.

The value of biodiesel refractive index ranges between (1.4400 and 1.4500), refractive index is measured using Refractometer.

Figure 12: Digital Refractometer to measure the refractive index.

Yield

The yield of any procedure is a strong indication of the success of the experiment. Yield is calculated using the following formula:

$$\%yield = \frac{V_{experimental}}{V_{theoretical}} \cdot 100$$

Where:

- V experimental: is the volume of the produced biodiesel from each sample (ml)
- V theoretical: theoretical volume of the produced biodiesel (ml)

Theoretical volume of biodiesel is calculated from the molar weight and density using the following relation:

$$Volume = \frac{Molar\ weight}{Density}$$

Molar weight of the standard biodiesel is approximately equals 857g/mol and the density is estimated to be 0.85g/ml from experiment.

CHAPTER IV: Results and Discussion

Tables and Figures

Tables

Table 9: demonstrates the volume of ethanol (ml) and the catalyst weight (g) for each sample, with the volume of the produced Glycerin (ml), Raw biodiesel (ml) and clean biodiesel (ml).

Sample	Ethanol Volume (ml)	NaOH weight (g)	Sunflower oil Volume (ml)	Total Volume (ml)	Glycerin Volume (ml)	Raw Biodiesel (ml)	Clean Biodiesel (ml)
1	60	0.8	200	260	25	220	201
2	90	0.8	200	290	32	240	210
3	120	0.8	200	320	32	268	253
4	60	1.0	200	260	31	215	199
5	90	1.0	200	290	33	239	227
6	120	1.0	200	320	28	283	275
7	60	1.2	200	260	39	199	181
8	90	1.2	200	290	36	244	225
9	120	1.2	200	320	19	294	269
10	60	1.5	200	260	50	185	179
11	90	1.5	200	290	37	242	229
12	120	1.5	200	320	10	307	289

Table 10: demonstrates density (g/ml), viscosity (cP), refractive index, theoretical volume of biodiesel (ml) and Yield for samples 1, 4,7,10 where the used ethanol volume equals 60ml

Sample	V biodiesel (ml)	Density (g/ml)	Viscosity (cP)	Refractive Index	V theo (ml)	Yield
1	201	0.82	3.95	1.4356	226.3425	0.888035
4	199	0.84	4.6	1.4551	220.953392	0.900642
7	181	0.85	4.16	1.4465	218.353941	0.828929
10	179	0.85	4.56	1.447	218.353941	0.81977

Table 11: demonstrates density (g/ml), viscosity (cP), refractive index, theoretical volume of biodiesel (ml) and Yield for samples 2,5,8,11 where the used ethanol volume equals 90ml.

Sample	V biodiesel (ml)	Density (g/ml)	Viscosity (cP)	Refractive Index	V theo (ml)	Yield
2	210	0.86	4.23	1.443	248.690751	0.84442
5	227	0.83	4.6	1.4437	257.679573	0.88093
8	225	0.84	4.16	1.4512	254.611959	0.88369
11	229	0.83	4.62	1.4521	257.679573	0.88870

Table 12: demonstrates density (g/ml), viscosity (cP), refractive index, theoretical volume of biodiesel (ml) and Yield for samples 3, 6,9,12 where the used ethanol volume equals 120ml.

Sample	V biodiesel (ml)	Density (g/ml)	Viscosity (cP)	Refractive Index	V theo (ml)	Yield
3	253	0.85	4.32	1.4433	298.417052	0.84780
6	275	0.86	4.51	1.4561	294.947087	0.93237
9	269	0.84	4.77	1.4498	301.969636	0.89081
12	289	0.86	4.55	1.4564	294.947087	0.97983

Figures

Figure 8: Yield values vs. different volumes of ethanol (ml).

Figure 9: Yield values vs. Different catalyst weights (g).

Figure 13: Refractive index values when changing the catalyst weight at 60ml volume

Figure 14: Refractive index values when changing the catalyst weight at 90ml volume

Figure 15: Refractive index values when changing the catalyst weight at 120ml volume

Figure 16: Viscosity values at different catalyst weights (volume=60ml)

Figure 17: Viscosity values at different catalyst weights (volume=90ml)

Figure 18: Viscosity values at different catalyst weights (volume=120ml)

Sample of Calculations

For sample 1:

Molar mass of sunflower oil = 876.16 g/mol

Sunflower oil density = 0.925 g/mol

Sunflower oil volume = 200 ml

Biodiesel standard density = 293g/mol

Sample 1 density = 0.82g/mol

$$\frac{200ml * 0.925g/mol}{876.16g/mol} = 0.21115mol$$

$$\frac{0.21115mol * 3 * 293g/mol}{0.82g/mol} = 260.87 = \text{theo } V \text{ of biodiesel}$$

$$Yield = \frac{V \text{ theo}}{V \text{ exp}} = \frac{260.87ml}{201ml} = 0.888035$$

Discussion

A transesterification reaction is a chemical reaction, where the triglycerides that are present in the oil are converted into usable biodiesel. The product of the transesterification reaction has generally a low value of viscosity. The reaction has two main steps which are the mixing of the reactants and the separation of the product. This reaction can be carried out using a batch reactor or a continuous reactor depending on the desired scale of production.

The lipids that are present in the oil are nonpolar lipids triacylglycerol's TAGs and FFAs free fatty acids. With the aid of a catalyst and alcohol fatty acids, ethyl esters are formed.

Figure 19: Transesterification reaction

The previous reaction occurs with the aid of a catalyst and under specific temperature.

As shown in the reaction Glycerol is formed as a by-product of the reaction. Glycerol esters have relatively low solubility compared to the main product, which can make the separation process easier. The separation process can be sped up using a centrifugation step. Excess alcohol will not react and will cause a delay in the separation process; however, the excess alcohol will not be removed from the reaction until the separation process has been achieved.

Figure 20: Flow sheet of biodiesel production process.

After the separation process, the ethyl esters mixture is neutralized and separated from impurities. For the neutralization acid is added, it reduces the amount of water needed for washing in addition to minimizing the possibility of soap formation during the reaction. the soap reacts with the acid to form fatty acids and hydrophilic salts. The hydrophilic

salts remain in the produced biodiesel whereas the fatty acids are removed during the washing process. The washing process ensures the removal of any unwanted materials from the product; such as salt, soap, catalyst.

As mentioned earlier the by-product from this reaction is glycerol, this glycerol contains a catalyst, excess alcohol, and soap. The presence of these impurities in the glycerol devalues its commercial potential and makes it to be hazardous waste. To increase its value the glycerol can be refined and separated into two layers the upper layer which is the glycerol and the bottom layer which consists of fatty acids that can be esterified and recycled back into the feedstock stream. These different processes can minimize the number of unwanted products.

The practical experiment that was conducted to simulate the production of biodiesel process was divided into multiple parts each part has different alcohol and catalyst ratio to study the effect of the changing variables on the properties of the produced biodiesel.

Table 9 represents the amount of the produced biodiesel before and after washing at different ratios of alcohol and catalyst. it is logical for the samples that contained higher volume of ethanol to produce more product. But it is also noticed for all samples that with the increase of the catalyst weight the volume of the product has also increased. This all goes back to the purpose of using a catalyst in the first place that is a faster, more efficient chemical reaction.

Tables 10,11,12 demonstrates the density, viscosity, refractive index and yield 60/90/120ml ethanol. All density data for all samples are considered within the normal range, this also goes to the viscosity and the refractive index values. As for the yield values it is noticed that the higher that ethanol volume the higher the yield value.

Figure 8 compares the yield values for each sample at different ethanol volume, with the increase of ethanol volume the yield increases as well.

Figure 9 shows the relation between the catalyst weight and yield. With the increase of catalyst the yield increases.

Figures 10, 11, 12 show the relation between the catalyst weight and refractive index, from graphs it can be seen that a higher catalyst weight increases the refractive index.

Figures 13, 14, 15 show the relation between the catalyst weight and the viscosity values, from graphs it can also be seen that the catalyst weight effects the viscosity proportionally

Sources of error

Throughout this work many samples had to be repeated for various reasons which considered being sources of error, such as

- Overheating the solution during the mixing process which resulted in instant separation between the oil and the alcohol/catalyst mixture.
- Due to limited resources one of two solutions had to be reheated more than once which affected the quality of the product.
- Not working in a completely low moisture environment resulted in the formation of soap during the reaction.
- Mechanical and systematic errors were present but can be considered negligible.
- Using 70% ethanol instead to 99% ethanol.

CHAPTER V: Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

In conclusion, biodiesel is (m) ethyl esters, the product of a transesterification of vegetable oils or animal fats (tallow). Historically, pure biodiesel has been used in diesel engines, but due to its properties that depend on several factors such as temperature, biodiesel blends are currently being used in some countries.

Biodiesel combustion has significantly lower CO₂ emissions when compared to Fossil fuel diesel. This reduction can reach 50%. Biodiesel emissions contain less particulate matter, CO and PAHs in addition to compounds that contain sulfur are nearly undetectable.

Due to the low emissions that are produced from the combustion of biodiesel, biodiesel is considered to be safer for usage.

Current used engines are not suitable for replacing fossil fuel diesel with biodiesel. Biodiesel can reduce the engine efficiency and due to its high viscosity it can cause plugging and delayed fuel injection. Nevertheless, further development of biodiesel will make it a better alternative than diesel.

The practical part of this work includes the biodiesel production from Sunflower oil (vegetable oil) and ethanol (alcohol) with the aid of a catalyst which is sodium hydroxide. The aim behind this study is to simplify the process of the biodiesel production and the impact of the oil: alcohol ratio, catalyst weight on the properties of the produced biodiesel and the percentage yield.

From the experimental results, the ratio between oil and ethanol has shown a direct proportion with the percentage yield of the product. As for the catalyst impact on the biodiesel production it has also shown direct proportion at volumes 90ml and 120ml but not at 60ml. These results cannot support a definitive conclusion; further studies should be made on a different scale to offer more reliable results.

The studied properties of the produced biodiesel are density, viscosity and refractive index. The values of these properties should be within a limit to imitate the fossil fuel diesel for an easier usage.

The produced biodiesel may contain impurities and unwanted properties, additives may be added during the reaction to guarantee a better outcome.

Furthermore, there are other methods to produce biodiesel from vegetable oils and animal fats such as Micro-emulsification and thermal cracking (pyrolysis)

Recommendations

The temperature of the reaction has a huge impact on the reaction itself and on the properties of the product. Hence, a heating and cooling system should be installed to maintain a constant temperature.

Although enzymatic catalysts are relatively expensive, nevertheless it should be used due to its properties to enhance the reaction as a whole and to enhance the products properties with higher yield values.

Pure ethanol should be used to eliminate water from forming soap through saponification reaction.

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Appendix

Figure 21: From Experiment (after mixing the sunflower oil with ethanol and NaOH)

Figure 22: Mixing sunflower oil with ethanol and NaOH using a magnetic stirrer on a hot plate.

Figure 23: Sunflower with ethanol and NaOH mixture in a separatory funnel.

Figure 24: Two layers in the separatory funnel, the top is biodiesel and the bottom is Glycerol.

Figure 25: Pure Biodiesel.

Chemical Safety Data: Ethanol

Common Synonyms: Grain alcohol, denatured; Ethyl alcohol, denatured; Ethyl hydroxide, denatured.

Formula: C_2H_5OH

Physical properties:

- Clear Liquid
- Oder alcohol like
- Melting Point/Range: $< -90\text{ }^\circ\text{C} / -130\text{ }^\circ\text{F}$
- Boiling Point/Range: $77.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C} / 170.8\text{ }^\circ\text{F}$
- Flash Point: $13.9\text{ }^\circ\text{C} / 57\text{ }^\circ\text{F}$
- Solubility: Soluble in water

Hazards identification

- Highly flammable liquid and vapor
- Causes serious eye irritation
- Suspected of causing cancer
- Suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child
- May cause damage to organs
- May cause drowsiness or dizziness

Stability and reactivity

- Stability: Stable under normal conditions.
- Conditions to Avoid: Incompatible products. Excess heat. Keep away from open flames, hot surfaces and sources of ignition.
- Incompatible Materials: Strong oxidizing agents, Acids, Acid anhydrides, Acid chlorides, Peroxides, Alkali metals.
- Hazardous Decomposition Products: Carbon monoxide (CO), Carbon dioxide (CO₂).
- Hazardous Polymerization: Hazardous polymerization does not occur.

Chemical Safety Data: Sodium Hydroxide

Chemical Formula: NaOH

Physical and Chemical Properties

- Physical State: Solid
- Appearance: white
- Odor: Odorless
- pH: 14 (5% aq soln)
- Vapor Pressure: 1 mm Hg @739 deg C
- Vapor Density: Not available.
- Evaporation Rate:Not available.
- Viscosity: Not available.
- Boiling Point: 1390 deg C @ 760 mmHg
- Freezing/Melting Point:318 deg C
- Decomposition Temperature:Not available.
- Solubility: Soluble.
- Specific Gravity/Density:2.13 g/cm³
- Molecular Formula:NaOH
- Molecular Weight:40

Potential Health Effects

- Eye: Causes eye burns. May cause blindness. May cause chemical conjunctivitis and corneal damage.
- Skin: Causes skin burns. May cause deep, penetrating ulcers of the skin.
- Ingestion: May cause severe and permanent damage to the digestive tract. Causes gastrointestinal tract burns. May cause perforation of the digestive tract. Causes severe pain, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and shock.
- Inhalation: Irritation may lead to chemical pneumonitis and pulmonary edema. Causes severe irritation of upper respiratory tract with coughing, burns, breathing difficulty, and possible coma. Causes chemical burns to the respiratory tract.
- Chronic: Prolonged or repeated skin contact may cause dermatitis. Effects may be delayed.

Chemical Safety Data: Phosphoric acid

Formula: H_3PO_4

Physical and chemical properties

- Appearance: clear, colorless liquid
- Odorless
- Vapor density: 3.4
- Melting/freezing point: 21C
- Boiling point: 158C
- Relative density 1.680
- Soluble in water

Hazard statements

- Corrosive to metals
- Cause severe skin burns and eye damage

Waste disposal recommendations:

Product/containers must not be disposed together with household garbage. Do not allow product to reach sewage system or open water. It is the responsibility of the waste generator to properly characterize all waste materials according to applicable regulatory entities.

Viscosity:

Viscosity was measure using a digital viscometer, with a 52 sized spindle.

The samples were tested at room temperature.

Table 13: Viscosity values from the viscometer

Sample	Viscosity	RPM	Percent
1	3.95	3	54.3%
2	4.23	2	25.4%
3	4.32	2	35.6%
4	4.6	2	52.9%
5	4.6	2	72.3%
6	4.51	2	61.7%
7	4.16	2	36.6%
8	4.16	2	46.2%
9	4.77	2	34.2%
10	4.56	2	64.8%
11	4.62	2	56.5%
12	4.55	2	29.6%

Density

Density values were calculated manually.

Table 14: Density values for biodiesel g/ml.

Sample	Empty Cylinder	Filled cylinder 25ml	Density g/ml
1	48.36	68.86	0.82
2	48.21	69.71	0.86
3	49.01	70.26	0.85
4	48.60	69.60	0.84
5	48.33	69.08	0.83
6	47.92	69.42	0.86
7	48.36	69.61	0.85
8	48.92	69.92	0.84
9	49.00	70.00	0.84
10	48.56	69.81	0.85
11	48.87	69.62	0.83
12	48.31	69.81	0.86

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Mass}}{\text{volume}} = \frac{\text{Mass of a filled cylinder} - \text{mass of an empty cylinder}}{\text{Volume of the biodiesel in cylinder}}$$

From sample #6

$$\text{Density} = \frac{69.42g - 47.92}{25ml} = \frac{21.5g}{25ml} = 0.86\left(\frac{g}{ml}\right)$$

Preparation of phosphoric acid 5% solution

The available phosphoric acid is 85% concentrated, the desired concentration is 5%.

To calculate the amount needed from 85% phosphoric acid to make 1 liter of 5% phosphoric acid.

$$85\% \cdot \rho \cdot V1 = 5\% \cdot \rho \cdot V2$$

$$\rho \text{ for } 85\% \text{ phosphoric acid} = 1.71 \text{ g/ml}$$

$$\rho \text{ for } 5\% \text{ phosphoric acid} = 1.04 \text{ g/ml}$$

$$V2 = 1000 \text{ ml}$$

$$V1 = \frac{1000 \text{ ml} \cdot \frac{1.04 \text{ g}}{\text{ml}} \cdot 0.05}{\frac{1.71 \text{ g}}{\text{ml}} \cdot 0.85} = 35.7 \text{ ml}$$